

Abstract

Euthanasia is a present-day problem in the field of medical as well as from a legal and religious perspective. Since there are different angles and opinions regarding this dilemma, it is necessary to know all its implications. Pakistan being an Islamic Republic, it is crucial for us to understand the religious angle that is in line with the medical and ethical dimension. The primary source of guidance for Muslims is the Holy Quran which is the most authentic and reliable. In this research we studied the Quranic verses regarding the rising problem of Euthanasia and our secondary sources consisted of Fatwas from credible Muslim scholars along with published articles regarding the Islamic point of view. The methodology that we used was a qualitative study research with derived results. Our findings proved that Euthanasia is not only forbidden from a religious outlook but also wrongful from an ethical and medical viewpoint.

Brief History of Euthanasia:

Euthanasia dates back to ancient Greek and Rome and several other religions of the world. In past, euthanasia was considered to be a way to accelerate the death of severely ill or hopeless patients. For example, a poisonous plant called the hemlock plant was used to hasten death in areas of Marseilles, the isle of Kea, and Athens. It also includes removal of pillow or laying patient on the ground, bleeding, and suffocation. Philosophers like Plato and Seneca the Elder supported euthanasia whereas Hippocrates opposed it. Techniques proposed by Questel were also opposed as they were against the laws of God and nature¹. The recommendation of the use of morphine by John Warren in the 1800s and the recommendation of the use of chloroform by Joseph Bullar in 1848 gave rise to the current debate on euthanasia. A school teacher named Samuel Williams in the Birmingham Speculative Club in England held the first debate on this topic².

Types of Euthanasia:

Euthanasia can be categorized into three main categories³:

1. Voluntary euthanasia: In this type, the patients want to die and It is linked to an individual's 'right to die'.

¹ Stolberg, Michael. "Active euthanasia in pre-modern society, 1500–1800: Learned debates and popular Practices." *Social history of medicine* 20, no. 2 (2007): 205-221.

² Emanuel, Ezekiel J. "The history of euthanasia debates in the United States and Britain." *Annals of internal medicine* 121, no. 10 (1994): 793-802.

³ LaFollette, Hugh, ed. *Ethics in practice: an anthology*. John Wiley & Sons, 2020.

2. Non-voluntary euthanasia: In this type, the patient's consent is available due to some reasons, for example, child euthanasia.

3. Involuntary euthanasia: In this type, euthanasia is carried out against a patient's will by his or her heirs or medical professionals who are examining or observing the patient's painful condition. All the above-mentioned types of Euthanasia are further classified into two types.

1. Active euthanasia: This type involves the usage of lethal substances or forces.

2. Passive euthanasia: This type involves the discontinuation of the patient's treatment. For example, switching off life support machines, disconnecting feed tubes, etc. drugs are also used such as painkillers which reduce the lifespan of the patient⁴.

Committing suicide because of pain:

One of the worst types of killing is to kill oneself (suicide) and the Holy Prophet has said about a person who committed suicide whether he was severely injured in a battle: *"My slave has caused death on himself hurriedly, so I forbid Paradise for him"*⁵

His funeral prayer was not performed by the Holy Prophet as is narrated by Sayyiduna Samurah (RA):

*"A man killed himself. So, the Prophet did not pray his funeral salah."*⁶

According to the teachings of Bible:

*Be not over much wicked, neither be thou foolish: why shouldst thou die before thy time?*⁷

Worldwide Current Legal Position of Euthanasia and Physician Assisted Suicide (PAS)

Passive and indirect euthanasia are reasonable practices that do not aim to take human life.⁸ The supporters of euthanasia propose that it is the right of people to give up on life to end their suffering if its beyond once ability to bear it. Islamic law gives humans the right to exercise decision making

⁴ Rachels, James. "Active and passive euthanasia." *Bioethics: An Introduction to the History, Methods, and Practice* (1975): 77-82.

⁵ Sahih Bukhari, Vol.2, p. 96, Hadith No. 1363

⁶ Jami' Tirmizi, Vol. 2, p.371, Hadith No. 1068.

⁷ Ecclesiastes, 7:17

⁸Verkerk, Marian, Eric van Wijlick, Johan Legemaate, and Alexander de Graeff. "A national guideline for palliative sedation in the Netherlands." *Journal of pain and symptom management* 34, no. 6 (2007): 666-670.

for themselves.⁹ Though, it needs to be exercised within certain boundaries without harming others. Euthanasia is a social issue; hence a fair balance shall be maintained among personal and societal impact while making such decisions. It is not physical pain, rather emotions which are a main factor of interest in euthanasia.¹⁰ A patient's desire to die can change over time, especially because of treating anxiety and pain. Therefore, ending life can not be a part of exercising autonomy because taking life itself ends the right to exercise autonomy.

Mostly, the attempts to legalize euthanasia have been trounced.¹¹ It is a disputation of principles and uprightness. According to a research, euthanasia gauges public support relatively more than that of doctors, who regard it as a useless practice.¹² As per an Asian study as well as a Malaysian study, most physicians disapprove such conducts, yet agree to discontinue the use of ventilators and such futile treatments when there is no hope of patient's survival.¹³

Despite opposition of euthanasia and EAS in most countries, some have passed laws that support it. If EAS becomes legalized through public referendums, it will not only have some huge implications, but it will also negatively influence minorities such as children, elderly, differently abled, people with aids, and cancer patients.¹⁴ Under current circumstances, medical practices shall be guided based on moral rather than political and economic forces.¹⁵

Religious Point of View

Majority of religions either oppose or reject EAS because of their belief in holiness of human life. Studies show that religious beliefs are a measure of hostility to euthanasia among people.¹⁶ An association among religious activity and a limiting attitude towards euthanasia has been recorded.¹⁷ Ethical people consider it a murder, while Hindus, Buddhists and Jain consider it unacceptable.

⁹ Aksoy, Sahin, and Abdurrahman Elmali. "The core concepts of the four principles of bioethics as found in Islamic tradition." *Med. & L.* 21 (2002): 211.

¹⁰ Van der Maas, Paul J., Gerrit Van Der Wal, Ilinka Haverkate, Carmen LM De Graaff, John GC Kester, Bregje D. Onwuteaka-Philipsen, Agnes Van Der Heide, Jacqueline M. Bosma, and Dick L. Willems. "Euthanasia, physician-assisted suicide, and other medical practices involving the end of life in the Netherlands, 1990–1995." *New England Journal of Medicine* 335, no. 22 (1996): 1699-1705.

¹¹ Emanuel, Ezekiel J., Diane L. Fairclough, and Linda L. Emanuel. "Attitudes and desires related to euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide among terminally ill patients and their caregivers." *Jama* 284, no. 19 (2000): 2460-2468.

¹² Seale, Clive. "Legalisation of euthanasia or physician-assisted suicide: survey of doctors' attitudes." *Palliative Medicine* 23, no. 3 (2009): 205-212.

¹³ Pioneering NUS study unveils what Singapore doctors say about caring for the dying. Available at: www.lienfoundation.org/pdf/news/. Accessed on Feb 20, 2012.

¹⁴ Pereira, Jose. "Legalizing euthanasia or assisted suicide: the illusion of safeguards and controls." *Current Oncology* 18, no. 2 (2011): 38-45.

¹⁵ Bachman, Jerald G., Kirsten H. Alcer, David J. Doukas, Richard L. Lichtenstein, Amy D. Corning, and Howard Brody. "Attitudes of Michigan physicians and the public toward legalizing physician-assisted suicide and voluntary euthanasia." *New England Journal of Medicine* 334, no. 5 (1996): 303-309.

¹⁶ Suarez-Almazor, Maria E., Michelle Belzile, and Eduardo Bruera. "Euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide: a comparative survey of physicians, terminally ill cancer patients, and the general population." *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 15, no. 2 (1997): 418-427.

¹⁷ Førde, Reidun, Olaf Gjerløw Aasland, and Erik Falkum. "The ethics of euthanasia—attitudes and practice among Norwegian physicians." *Social science & medicine* 45, no. 6 (1997): 887-892.

¹⁸Likewise, believers of one God consider it a sin.¹⁹ Islam guides all spheres of human life and uses three sources of sacred law that are Quran, Hadith, and Ijtihad for decision making purpose within the boundaries of ethics.²⁰ It is evident in Quran that guarding life is a duty of all believers. "Do not kill yourselves for verily Allah has been to you most Merciful" (Qur'an 4:29). "Do not take life which God has made sacred except in the course of Justice" (Qur'an 17:33). "Anyone who has killed a fellow human except in lieu of murder or mischief on earth, it would be as he slew the whole mankind"(Qur'an 5:32). According to these verses, there is high reward for people who save a life because saving one life is like saving entire mankind and vice versa.²¹ Islam has not only prohibited suicide but has also kept severe punishment for that. "And whoever commits that (suicide) through aggression and injustice, we shall cast him into the Fire, and that is easy for Allah" (Qur'an 4:30). Similarly, it says; "And spend in the cause of Allah and do not throw yourselves into destruction and do good. Truly, Allah loves the good-doers" (Qur'an 2:195). In case of killing a patient in the name of euthanasia, the doctor will be held accountable.

According to a hadith, seeking treatment is recommended, but it is permissible to stop the treatment if it is not effective. "O, servants of Allah, seek treatment, for Allah has not sent down any illness without sending down its treatment."²²

An individual can not die unless the Creator wills. "it is not given to any soul to die, but with the permission of Allah at an appointed time" (Qur'an 3:145). Muslim scholars such as Sheikh Yusuf al-Qaradawi have spoken against euthanasia, he said; "This act [euthanasia] is islamically forbidden for it encompasses a positive role on the part of the physician to end the life of the patient and hasten his death via lethal injection, electric shock, a sharp weapon or any other way. This is an act of killing, and, killing is a major sin and thus forbidden in Islam, the religion of pure mercy".²³ *Ajal*, is completely under the control of Allah and since the human has no say or control over it; the human should not speed up the process of *Ajal*. This principle applies equally on matters of suicide, homicide, or genocide. Despite having autonomy and free will this is not permissible to humans as:

A. humans have no control over life; and

B. taking life will cause harm to the family and society in general.²⁴

Believers must not lose hope in mercy of their Creator when they fall sick, since it is not destructive rather beneficial, and it is just a testing ground. However, they can seek treatment as commanded

¹⁸ Coward, Harold G., Julius Lipner, and Katherine K. Young. *Hindu ethics: Purity, abortion, and euthanasia*. SUNY Press, 1989.

¹⁹ Engelhardt, H. Tristram, and Ana Smith Iltis. "End-of-life: the traditional Christian view." *The Lancet* 366, no. 9490 (2005): 1045-1049.

²⁰ Daar, Abdallah S., and A. Khitamy. "Bioethics for clinicians: 21. Islamic bioethics." *Cmaj* 164, no. 1 (2001): 60-63.

²¹ Sachedina Islam. In: Reich WT, editor. *Encyclopedia of bioethics*. Rev ed. New York: Simon and Schuster/Prentice Hall International 1995:1289-97.

²² Sunan Abi Dawuud. Vol. 2, Book 27, Kitab al-Tibb, Chapter 1, Hadith 3855. Available at: <http://www.muhammad.org>. Accessed February 20, 2012.

²³ Al-Qaradawi Y. Question and answer about Euthanasia. In: Islam online site. Available at: http://www.islamonline.net/servlet/Satellite?cid=1119503544774&pagename=IslamOnline-English-Ask_Scholar/FatwaE/FatwaEAskTheScholar. Accessed April 5, 2012.

²⁴ Narimisa, Mehran. "Euthanasia in Islamic views." *European Scientific Journal* (2014).

by Allah and His messenger. "Be sure that We shall test you with something of fear and hunger, some loss in goods or lives or the fruits of your toil, but give glad tidings to those who patiently persevere" (Qur'an 2:155).²⁵ Allah is with the patient; "Those who patiently preserve will truly receive a reward without measure" (Qur'an 39:10). "And bear in patience whatever (ill) maybe fall you: this, behold, is something to set one's heart upon" (Qur'an 31:17). Prophet Muhammad has said "When the believer is afflicted with pain, even that of a prick of a thorn or more, God forgives his sins, and his wrongdoings are discarded as a tree sheds off its leaves."²⁶ People who commit suicide ease their suffering of this world, but open doors for problems in the hereafter, such as not entering paradise.²⁷

Two main bullets can well summarize arguments of Islam against euthanasia; a) Human life is sacred, b) The Creator solely decides lifeline of every individual.²⁸ Sunni as well as Shia have no contradiction over euthanasia being forbidden in Islam. Humans should neither advance nor delay death. Muslims are not in favor of euthanasia and believe that they should not interfere in Allah's decision.

In Islam and international intellectual literature, there is negative stance regarding life's active termination²⁹. It is radically disapproved and forbidden on grounds of multiple convictions and theological arguments. The willingness to die voluntarily is also unrecognized by Islamic Jurisprudence based on plausible interpretation of Holy Quran. The two main reasons which present Islamic argument that opposes euthanasia are; Life is sanctified and euthanasia and suicide are not among the reasons for killing that are permitted and Allah is the decision maker who decides about life tenure of people. Life is considered a divine trust that cannot be terminated through passive or active intervention, in accordance with Islamic teaching. According to all Islamic scholars, be it from Sunni and Shiite schools, active euthanasia is prohibited. The ajal, moment of death, is under Allah's control, no one can rush or slow down this moment. This forbidden on life implements on all forms whether suicide, self, or other genocide or homicide. The idea of freedom, individual choice and autonomy is not applicable due to following reasons:

1. Humans do not have right on life
2. Ending one's life will negatively affect the family and society as a whole

The idea of God's omniscience and omnipotence regarding life and death is validated by normative Islamic literature. God gives and takes life³⁰, which infers human impossibility and limitedness to predict one's death moment³¹. An unconditional belief in predestination is found

²⁵ Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "Right to Die?": Muslim Views about End-of-Life Decisions." *Internet] Available from: <http://www.people.virginia.edu/~aas/article/article3/htm>* (2006).

²⁶ Hathout, Hassan. "Islamic basis for biomedical ethics." (1992).

²⁷ Goma Ali. Ethics of Euthanasia. Available at:<http://www.islamopediaonline.org/fatwa/egypts-darul-ifta-euthanasia>. Accessed April 5,2012.

²⁸ Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "End-of-life: the Islamic view." *The lancet* 366, no. 9487 (2005): 774-779.

²⁹ (Broeckert and Chamsi-Pasha 2009;2010a;2010b;2015)

³⁰ (Al-Jeilani, Atighetchi, et al. 1987;2007;2008;2016)

³¹ (Al-Jeilani, Lapidus and Rahman 1987;1996;1998)

in Islam and happening of death is ascribed to desire of God³². It is argued by many scholars that everything is created by God and person's life span is also determined by God³³. This conflicts with the non-religious notion of right-to-die. Furthermore, it is stated that emphasis of west on self-determination as a right is limited according to Islamic viewpoint as person's life is under God's control and he has the right to decide it. According to this perspective euthanasia is viewed as an act of blasphemy and refusing right of God over lives³⁴.

There is clear emphasis of normative Islamic literature on teleological perspective. Every action will be judged by person's intention, so suicide will lead to everlasting punishment in hell³⁵.

Muslims are suggested to be familiar of achieving good marks by confronting suffering and illness that ultimately opens the road to heaven³⁶. Islamic viewpoint guarantees that the belief in hereafter and predestination helps Muslims to survive severe illnesses³⁷. According to this perspective euthanasia or assisted suicide is acceptable option.

Sanctity of human life also offers an argument against euthanasia and assisted suicide. Great value is attributed to human life preservation as it is among Islamic laws objectives which includes preservation of life, mind, faith, progeny and property³⁸. High importance is given to taking care of life and body as they are regarded as trust of God³⁹. Various scholars authenticate that the relationship of humans with body is in terms of vicegerency which means that body is a loan to human rather than his ownership, in Islam⁴⁰. Generally, treatment is optional or permissible if beneficial but if the treatment is futile then it is discouraged⁴¹. Therefore, assisted death and euthanasia are not a choice.

Attitude towards assisted suicide and euthanasia

It was argued that euthanasia acceptance has a tendency to decrease with age and increase with education level⁴². According to the study performed, some differences were observed in age but

³² Rispler-Chaim, Vardit. Islamic medical ethics in the twentieth century. Vol. 46. Brill, 1993

³³ Atighetchi, Dariusch. *Islamic bioethics: problems and perspectives*. Vol. 31. Dordrecht: Springer, 2007.

³⁴ Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "End-of-life: the Islamic view." *The lancet* 366, no. 9487 (2005): 774-779.

³⁵ Brockopp, J. E. 2004. Islamic ethics of life. Abortion, war and euthanasia. Studies in Comparative Religion. Columbia, SC: University of South Carolina Press.

³⁶ Al-Shahri, Mohammad Zafir. "Islamic theology and the principles of palliative care." *Palliative & supportive care* 14, no. 6 (2016): 635-640.

³⁷ Baider, Lea. "Cultural diversity: family path through terminal illness." *Annals of Oncology* 23 (2012): iii62-iii65.

³⁸ Al-Bar, Mohammed Ali, and Hassan Chamsi-Pasha. *Contemporary bioethics: Islamic perspective*. Springer Nature, 2015.

³⁹ Ghaly, M. 2015. Euthanasia. In *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, ed. K. Fleet, G. Kramer, D. Matringe, J. Nawas, and E. Rowson. London, UK: Brill Online

⁴⁰ Cassidy, Jane. "Islamic Medical Association." *BMJ* 343 (2011)

Van Den Branden, Stef, and Bert Broeckaert. "Necessary interventions: Muslim views on pain and symptom control in English Sunni e-Fatwas." *Ethical Perspectives* 17, no. 4 (2010).

⁴¹ Saiyad, Saleem. "Islamic Perspectives." *JIMA* 41 (2009): 109.

⁴² Cohen, Joachim, Isabelle Marcoux, Johan Bilsen, Patrick Deboosere, Gerrit Van der Wal, and Luc Deliens. "European public acceptance of euthanasia: socio-demographic and cultural factors associated with the acceptance of euthanasia in 33 European countries." *Social science & medicine* 63, no. 3 (2006): 743-756.

Cohen, Joachim, Isabelle Marcoux, Johan Bilsen, Patrick Deboosere, Gerrit Van der Wal, and Luc Deliens. "Trends in acceptance of euthanasia among the general public in 12 European countries (1981–1999)." *The European Journal of Public Health* 16, no. 6 (2006): 663-669.

in socioeconomic status between first generation and second generation and education level, there was no difference in their opinion. There was no such difference in attitudes of elderly and middle-aged women or the ones who did or did not confronted with severe illness (either in immediate environment or personally) towards euthanasia. The emphasis of middle-aged women on eschatological and theological notions was of same extent as preceding generation. The arguments made were consistent with normative Islamic views⁴³ Firstly, assisted suicide and euthanasia was regarded suicide or murder. Secondly, there was strong emphasis on God's omniscience and omnipotence and had a belief that ultimate author of life and death, person's life period and cure and illness. Thirdly, some people referred to vicegerency of a humans, that infers human body and life and body are a trust from God so they should take care of them. Fourthly, teleological perspective was also highlighted as they had belief that through active termination of life they will have to bear serious punishments in afterlife. However some middle-aged and elderly participants mentioned that God possess the knowledge and the autonomy to judge human beings. Attitude of understanding and compassion was reflected by around one-third of participants but they also acknowledged that euthanasia contradicts belief of Islam.

Islamic Code of Medical Ethics

Physicians respected and held in high esteem all around the world. After Allah's protection, physicians are next in line who are entrusted with the lives of human beings in this world and they are responsible for protecting and guarding it. The immense level of trust in physicians that they would always do the best for their patients. This trust and respect led to doctors being labelled as "little gods".⁴⁴

The Islamic Code of Medical Ethics says, "In his/her defense of life, however, the doctor is well advised to realize his limit and not transgress it. If it is scientifically certain that life cannot be restored, then it is futile to diligently keep the patient in a vegetative state by heroic means or to preserve the patient by deep freezing or other artificial methods. It is the process of life that the doctor aims to maintain and not the process of dying. In any case, the doctor shall not take a positive measure to terminate the patient's life".⁴⁵ Article 61 and article 62 are two articles of "The Islamic Code for Medical and Health Ethics" that are committed to Euthanasia and Physician-Assisted Death.⁴⁶ Since the nature of mercy-killing is that of crime, hence it is not reasonable from an Islamic and Ethical point of view. However, there are instances if a patient is declared brain-dead, the withdrawal of life-support would be allowed in that case in order to use the resources for another patient whose chances of survival exist. Patients who are subject to other

⁴³ Baeke, Goedele. "Religion and ethics at the end of life. A qualitative empirical study among elderly Jewish and Muslim women in Antwerp (Belgium)." (2012).

⁴⁴ Narimisa, Mehran. "Euthanasia in Islamic views." *European Scientific Journal* (2014).

⁴⁵ Fosarelli, Pat. "The Sanctity of Human Life." *JAMA* 298, no. 24 (2007): 2914-2920.

⁴⁶ Aramesh, Kiarash, and Heydar Shadi. "Euthanasia: an Islamic ethical perspective." (2007): 35-38.

illnesses or abnormalities are regarded as human beings whose lives are sacred from an Islamic point of view.⁴⁷

The idea of God's omniscience and omnipotence regarding life and death is validated by normative Islamic literature. God gives and takes life⁴⁸, which infers human impossibility and limitedness to predict one's death moment⁴⁹. An unconditional belief in predestination is found in Islam and happening of death is ascribed to desire of God⁵⁰. It is argued by many scholars that everything is created by God and person's life span is also determined by God⁵¹. This conflicts with the non-religious notion of right-to-die. Furthermore, it is stated that emphasis of west on self-determination as a right is limited according to Islamic viewpoint as person's life is under God's control and he has the right to decide it⁵². According to this perspective euthanasia is viewed as an act of blasphemy and refusing right of God over lives⁵³.

There is clear emphasis of normative Islamic literature on teleological perspective. Every action will be judged by person's intention. Therefore, suicide will lead to everlasting punishment in hell. Muslims are suggested to be familiar of achieving good marks by confronting suffering and illness that ultimately opens the road to heaven. Islamic viewpoint guarantees that the belief in hereafter and predestination helps Muslims to survive severe illnesses⁵⁴. According to this perspective euthanasia or assisted suicide is acceptable option.

Sanctity of human life also offers an argument against euthanasia and assisted suicide. Great value is attributed to human life preservation as it is among Islamic laws objectives which includes preservation of life, mind, faith, progeny and property. High importance is given to taking care of life and body as they are regarded as trust of God. Various scholars authenticate that the relationship of humans with body is in terms of vicegerency which means that body is a loan to human rather than his ownership, in Islam⁵⁵. Generally, treatment is optional or permissible if beneficial but if the treatment is futile then it is discouraged⁵⁶. Therefore, assisted death and euthanasia are not a choice.

⁴⁷ (Narimisa 2014)

⁴⁸ Al-Jeilani, M. 1987. Pain: Points of view of Islamic theology. *Acta Neurochirurgica Supplementum* 38:132–35. doi:10.1007/978-3-7091-6975-9_24

⁴⁹ (Al-Jeilani, Lapidus and Rahman 1987;1996;1998)

⁵⁰ Al-Shahri, M. 2016. Islamic theology and the principles of palliative care. *Palliative and Supportive Care* 14 (6):635–40. doi:10.1017/S1478951516000080.

⁵¹ Van den Branden, Stef, and Bert Broeckaert. "Living in the hands of God. English Sunni e-fatwas on (non-) voluntary euthanasia and assisted suicide." *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy* 14, no. 1 (2011): 29-41.

⁵² Ayuba, M. A. 2016. Euthanasia: A muslim's perspective. *Scriptura* 115 (0):1–13. doi:10.7833/115-0-1175

⁵³ Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "End-of-life: the Islamic view." *The lancet* 366, no. 9487 (2005): 774-779. Ahaddour, Chaïma, Stef Van den Branden, and Bert Broeckaert. "'God is the giver and taker of life': Muslim beliefs and attitudes regarding assisted suicide and euthanasia." *AJOB empirical bioethics* 9, no. 1 (2018): 1-11.

⁵⁴ Baider, Lea. "Cultural diversity: family path through terminal illness." *Annals of Oncology* 23 (2012): iii62-iii65.

⁵⁵ Brockopp, J. E. 2004. Islamic ethics of life. Abortion, war and euthanasia. Studies in Comparative Religion. Columbia, SC: University of South Carolina Press

⁵⁶ (Saiyad, et al. 2009;2013;2015;2016)

Fatwas by Scholars

Renowned Muslim scholars including Mufti Shaikh Abdul Aziz bin Abdullah bin Baz, the top jurisprudential authority of Saudi Arabia headed by Sheikh Bin Baz, Sheikh Yusuf alQaradawi, Ayatollah Khamanei, and Ayatollah Nuri Hamadani have given fatwas against Euthanasia.⁵⁷

As per grand Mufti of Egypt, Euthanasia is prohibited whether the doctors decides or the patient himself decides to end life to ease pain. The Islamic Medical Association (IMA) also has the same stance. The Islamic code of medical ethics encompasses, "Mercy killing, like suicide, finds no support except in the atheistic way of thinking that believes that our life on this earth is followed by void. The claim of killing for painful hopeless illness is also refuted, for there is no human pain that cannot be largely conquered by medication or by suitable neurosurgery."⁵⁸

The abundance of medication from Islamic Perspective:

Holy Prophet ordered for medication and to adopt means to cure diseases and said:

*"Make use of medical treatment, for Allah has not made a disease without appointing a remedy for it, with the exception of one disease, namely old age"*⁵⁹.

Hence, medication should be given priority and is not considered against trust in Allah through consensus among Fuqaha. Holy Prophet explained the real face of trust in Allah:

Hadhrat Anas bin Malik reported that someone asked, "*O Messenger of Allah! shall I tether it and trust in Allah or untie it and place trust in Allah?*" He said: "*Tie it and trust in Allah.*"⁶⁰

Depending on the nature of the disease and its treatment methods, medication may be compulsory, preferable, abominable, or forbidden⁶¹. The diseases are categorized into two types:

1. Diseases that may cause death or a loss of limb⁶².
2. Diseases that may not kill or cause a loss of limb⁶³.

Similarly, treatments are also classified into the following types:

⁵⁷ Aramesh, Kiarash, and Heydar Shadi. "Euthanasia: an Islamic ethical perspective." (2007): 35-38.

⁵⁸ The sanctity of human life. In: Islamic code of ethics. In Islamset site. Available at: <http://www.islamset.com/ethics/code/cont2.html>. Accessed April 4, 2012.

⁵⁹ Sunan Abi Dau'd, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No.3357, Jami' Al-Tirmizi, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No. 1961, Sunan Ibn e Majah, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No. 3427.

⁶⁰ Al- Tirmizi, Ch. Sifatil Qiyama, Hadith No. 2517, he added that this Hadith is Gharib(unusual).

⁶¹ Nida, Muhammad Naeem, Maut ud Dmagh(Bait ut Tibb wal Islam, Dar ul fikr), p. 197.

⁶² Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁶³ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

1. Treatment that affirms the benefit⁶⁴.
2. Treatment that is assumed to be beneficial⁶⁵.
3. Treatment having the fantasy of benefit⁶⁶.

If it is certain that the treatment will cure the patient otherwise the patient might be in danger of losing his life or losing his limb, the treatment is compulsory and cannot be refused by the patient as if he does refuse the treatment, he would be committing a great sin as agreed by all scholars⁶⁷. Similarly, treatment becomes mandatory when a patient has a contagious disease for which treatment is available or a non-contagious disease for which treatment is available. The patient is not allowed to refuse treatment in these conditions nor his guardians are allowed to stop the treatment as it is a threat to not only himself but to others as well. Prophet Muhammad said:

*“There should be neither harming nor reciprocating harm”*⁶⁸. and treatment for fearsome diseases is compulsory according to the order of Allah:

*“and do not put yourselves into destruction”*⁶⁹.

The above-mentioned views prove that passive euthanasia is not allowed in Islam.

Boundaries of Doctor’s authority:

Performing euthanasia is a violation of a doctor’s duty of saving the lives of patients. This may reduce the doctor’s credentials and make his expertise questionable. A doctor who gives a lethal dose to his patients is considered to be an unlearned doctor⁷⁰ by the Islamic jurists and is to be banned from medical practice according to Hanafi Fuqaha⁷¹. In the case of a patient willing to end their life, Hanafi Fuqaha allows the doctor to withdraw from the treatment while receiving the payment for the period he treated the patient⁷². According to Fuqaha, the doctor is allowed to treat

⁶⁴ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁶⁵ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁶⁶ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁶⁷Mubarak, Qais bin Muhammad A'l Al-Sheikh, Al-Tadavi wal Mas'ooliyyah Al-Taibbiyyah fi Al-Sharia'h Al-Islamiyyah(Mu'ssasat ur Rayyan, 1997), p. 99.

⁶⁸ Ibn Majjah, Hadith No. 2340-2342.

⁶⁹ Surah Al-Baqara, 2:195.

⁷⁰ Lajnatul Ulema(Scholar’s Committee), Al-Mosu'h Al-Fiqhiyyah Al-Kuwaitiyyah (Wazarat ul Aoqaf wa Al-Sho'on Al-Islamiyyah, Darus Salasil, Kuwait), v. 17, p. 101

⁷¹ Ibid

⁷² Ibid, v.1, p. 300

a patient and save his life if the patient is on the verge of death and is not conscious to give his permission. In this condition, if the doctor does not treat the patient, he is considered to violate his duty and is prone to legal penalty⁷³. If a patient is conscious to give his permission, then the doctor needs the patient's permission⁷⁴.

Killing a person who is on the verge of death:

Killing a person on the verge of death to ease his pain is still considered killing although he may have killed him out of mercy⁷⁵. As it is a universal Islamic rule that:

*"certainty cannot be faded away by doubts"*⁷⁶

and it is also a universal rule that:

*"that there is no place for fantasy"*⁷⁷

The concept of ending a person's life to provide him relief is doubtful as our lives do not end with this worldly life but we also would be provided with life in the Qayama⁷⁸. It is narrated in a hadith:

*"A man was inflicted with wounds and he committed suicide, and so Allah said: My slave has caused death on himself hurriedly, so I forbid Paradise for him"*⁷⁹

The decision of court:

It is the responsibility of the court to protect the rights of the citizens of the country regardless of their social class and to not support merciless decisions of death without having committed any crime⁸⁰. Prophet Muhammad said in the case of Fatima Makhzoomia (R.A) when she committed theft:

⁷³ Ibn Qadamah, Abu Muhammad Muwaffiq ud Din Al-Muqaddisi (620A.H.), AIMughni, (Maktabat ul Cairo), v.5, p. 390

⁷⁴ Ibid, and Al-Mosu'h Al-Fiqhiyyah Al-Kuwaitiyyah v.3, p. 154

⁷⁵ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁷⁶ Ulema Committee formed by Usmani Caliphate, Majallat ul Ahkam Al- Adaliyyah, (Noor Muhammad Karkhana Tijarat e Kutub, A'ram Bagh, Karachi), v.1, p.16

⁷⁷ Ibid, v.1, p. 25.

⁷⁸ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁷⁹ Sahih Bukhari, v2, p 96, Hadith No. 1363

⁸⁰ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

*"O people! Those who came before you were only destroyed because when one of their nobles stole, they let him off but when one of the weak people among them stole, they would carry out the punishment on him. By Allah, if Fatimah the daughter of Muhammad was to steal, I would cut off her hand"*⁸¹

Authority of social agencies:

Social agencies hold a materialistic view of human life and propagate the concept of euthanasia, putting forth the argument that a person at his death bed is not beneficial to his family or society. Such a mindset may take humanity to the period of ignorance before Islam may result in the degeneration of the whole world⁸².

*"When it is said to them: Do not spread disorder on the earth, they say: We are but reformers. Beware, it is, in fact, they who spread disorder, but they do not appreciate"*⁸³

These agencies have launched websites with the main agenda of reducing the population and protecting the earth through ways like suicide, abortion, cannibalism, and sodomy. Regarding this, the Quran says:

*"Do not kill your children for fear of poverty. We provide sustenance to them and to you, too. Killing them is a great sin indeed"*⁸⁴.

The Prophet (SAW) has also proved the sacredness of human life by taking swear commitment from his companions not to kill their children⁸⁵ and not to kill each other⁸⁶. (54) (55)

Euthanasia as a slippery slope:

According to a survey held in United States, about 16% of more than 10,000 physicians admitted that they performed euthanasia on the family's demands. In which about 16% of more than 10,000 physicians admitted that they halted life sustaining therapy on the demand of family although they

⁸¹ Sunan Ibn e Majjah, V3, p 582, Hadith No. 254.

⁸² Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁸³ Surah Al- Baqara, 2 : 11-12.

⁸⁴ Surah Al-Asra, 103 : 31

⁸⁵ Sahih Bukhari, vol.1, p.18, Hadith No.18.

⁸⁶ Ahmad, Abu Abdullah Ahmad bin Muhammad bin Hambal(241 A.H.), (Mu'assasat ur Risalah 1421/2001), v.37, p. 341, Hadith No. 2668.

thought it was premature. 46% physicians agreed that the physicians assisted suicide in USA⁸⁷. Euthanasia is not allowed in Turkey but 43.8% oncologists did not object it, 41.5% performed Euthanasia secretly and 50.6% of the oncologists withdraw themselves from the treatment⁸⁸.

Bearing pain and hardship is always rewarded:

When a patient bears pain and suffering Allah forgives his sins

The Prophet (SAW) said: *“No fatigue, nor disease, nor sorrow, nor sadness, nor hurt, nor distress befalls a Muslim, even if it were the prick he receives from a thorn, but that Allah expiates some of his sins for that”*⁸⁹

The Prophet (SAW) said: *“for no Muslim is afflicted with any harm but that Allah will remove his sins as the leaves of a tree fall down”*⁹⁰

The Prophet said: *“No calamity befalls a Muslim but that Allah expiates some of his sins because of it, even though it were the prick he receives from a thorn”*⁹¹

Allah's Messenger (peace & blessing be upon him) said: *“Be moderate and stand firm in trouble that falls to the lot of a Muslim (as that) is an expiation for him; even stumbling on the path or the pricking of a thorn are an expiation for him”*⁹².

The Holy Prophet said: *“Don't curse fever for it expiates the sin of the posterity of Adam just as furnace removes the alloy of iron”*⁹³

Allah's Messenger (SAW) said: *“Trials do not cease to afflict the believing men and the believing women in their person, their children and their property till they meet Allah and on them is no sin”*⁹⁴

⁸⁷ Kane, Leslie. "MA, Exclusive Ethics Survey Results: Doctors Struggle With Tougher-Than-Ever Dilemmas." *Medscape Medical Ethics* 2010 (2010)..

⁸⁸Mayda, Atilla Senih, Erdem Özkara, and Funda Corapçıoğlu. "Attitudes of oncologists toward euthanasia in Turkey." *Palliative & supportive care* 3, no. 3 (2005): 221-225.

⁸⁹ Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 114, Hadith No. 5641.

⁹⁰ Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 115, Hadith No. 5647.

⁹¹ Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 114, Hadith No. 5640.

⁹² Sahih Muslim, vol. 4, p.1993, Hadith No. 2574.

⁹³ Sahih Muslim, vol. 4, p. 1993, Hadith No. 2575.

⁹⁴ Al-Tirmizi, Muhammad bin Esa bin Saura(279 A.H.), Sunan Al-Tirmizi, (Darul Gharb Al- Islami, Beirut, 1998), vol. 4, p. 180, Hadith No. 2572.

Allah's Messenger (peace & blessing be upon him) said: *"If a Muslim runs a thorn or (gets into trouble) severe than this, there is assured for him (a higher) rank and his sins are obliterated"*⁹⁵

The legal status of DNR:

DNR or do not resuscitate is an order in the patient's file according to which the doctor is prohibited to resuscitate if the patient's heart fails. The techniques used to resuscitate have side effects including broken ribs, fractures, ruptured spleen, brain damage etc. The Islamic law forbids the patient to make the decision of DNR and leaves the decision to the medical expert examining the patient. Positive and negative effects of the situation have to be examined by the Medical experts before making any decision so as to achieve the maximum benefit according to Fiqhi Maxim⁹⁶.

A severe harm, if necessary, should be eliminated by adopting less harm.

And

*certainty does not vanish by a doubt*⁹⁷

The intentional pain or fracture (when the benefit is not clear) is not allowed in Islamic Law as Prophet Muhammad (peace & blessing be upon him) has not allowed it even in the case of a deceased person:

*No person can decide to deprive a person of the right of saving his life even though he is unconscious or severely mentally retarded or damaged brain as the life is bestowed by Allah (Subhanahu Wa Taa'la)*⁹⁸.

According to Islamic law, parents are not allowed to decide death for their newborn child.

The doctrine of double effect:

This doctrine states that something having bad side effects is ethically accepted if it is morally good as the intention was of doing good only⁹⁹. This doctrine is widely used in medical science. Many doctors are prone to misuse this doctrine as they give heavy doses of morphine and other drugs to ease the patient's pain but these might shorten the patient's lifespan¹⁰⁰. It is not allowed

⁹⁵ Sahih Muslim, vol. 4., p 1991, Hadith No. 2572

⁹⁶ Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

⁹⁷ Majallah Al-Ahkam Al-Adaliyyah, vol.1, p.16.

⁹⁸ Sunan Ibn e Majah, v.1. P. 516, Hadith No. 1616

⁹⁹ <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/double-effect/>.

¹⁰⁰ <http://hospicecare.com/about-iahpc/publications/ethical-issues-2/otherpublications/ the-double-effect-of-pain-medication-separating-myth-from-reality/>.

to use such sources given that any better treatment is available so that the lesser evil of all evils is adopted by the doctor.

As the intentions of a person determine his actions, it may not be allowed to use this doctrine to kill a patient,

The reward of deeds depends upon the intentions¹⁰¹

The intentions of a doctor may be doubted in a case if the dose of painkillers accedes to the medically recommended dose as it may result in the death of the patient.

International Islamic convention for medical ethics or health:

The International Islamic Convention passed the following resolution about Euthanasia under section 62: “Human life is sacred and it is not permitted to squander it except the limits defined by the Islamic Law and Sharia, and all these matters are out of the boundaries of the medical profession. It is not allowed to the medical experts to participate in the process of ending the life of patient although it is in the name of mercy.” Particularly the following situations are known as mercy killing:

1. Deliberately killing people wanting to end their life through their will and wish.
2. Suicide assisted by Physicians.
3. Parents killing their infants who have congenital deformities, limiting their life.

Section 63:

The following situations are excluded from mercy killing:

1. stopping the patient’s treatment when it is declared of no benefit by a committee of specialized doctors i.e. removing exhilaration instruments.
2. Disregarding the start of treatment when it appears to have no benefit.
3. Providing strong treatment for removal of severe pain, being aware of the threat to patient’s life it may cause^{102, 103}.

Conclusion:

¹⁰¹ Sahih Bukhari, v1, p.

¹⁰² <http://www.sehha.com/medical/IslamicCodeEthics5b.htm>

¹⁰³ Al-Meesaq Al-Islami Al-‘alami lil Akhlaqiyyat At Tibbiyyah, Ch. 5, Al-Qadhaya Alljtima’yyah, Taiseer ul Maut Ao Qatl il marhamah, Course.62

Human life is regarded as the most magnificent and precious amongst the creations of Allah- “*Ashraf-ul-Makhlukat*”. Great significance has been placed on the human life in the Holy Quran as its creation is described step by step especially the creation of spirit- “*Khalqan Aakhar*”. “Blessed be the Best of creators!” (Qur’an: 23:14).¹⁰⁴ The gift of life must be valued and regarded. The killing of an innocent person is not only considered as a criminal act, but also as an offence to the creation. Euthanasia, also known as the act of mercy-killing, is fundamentally disapproved and forbidden due to multiple theological and ethical arguments. The will of a human being to die voluntarily is also unrecognized by Islamic Jurisprudence based on the guidance of Holy Quran. Muslims are always recommended to remain steadfast in times of hardship and trials. Even though some prolonged illnesses can be painful, humans should accept it as their worldly test and have faith as Allah has promised a reward for their difficulties.

From a legal and medical viewpoint Euthanasia is still considered as a criminal offence. The responsibility of physician revolves around protecting and acting in the best interest of their patients. Letting a patient die voluntarily is against the practice of a doctor both legally and ethically. There has been a difference of opinions among the medical practitioners regarding Euthanasia, which is also secretly adopted by some Muslim countries such as Turkey. Despite the justifications, each patient has an equal right to medical treatment as long as possible and can only be withdrawn in case of critical situations such as ‘brain-dead’ patients. This is only applicable to save and use the resources for patients who have a better chance of surviving.

The act of Euthanasia should be condemned as it is wrong both for the patient and the person performing it. It is considered illegal in majority of the countries and punishable. It can be a source of discomfort for some people in this world for example the doctors who’d be held responsible for performing it. In case of Muslims, staying firm in their faith is an integral part of their belief whereas the act of Euthanasia portrays otherwise.

Bibliography:

- Stolberg, Michael. "Active euthanasia in pre-modern society, 1500–1800: Learned debates and popular Practices." *Social history of medicine* 20, no. 2 (2007): 205-221.
- Emanuel, Ezekiel J. "The history of euthanasia debates in the United States and Britain." *Annals of internal medicine* 121, no. 10 (1994): 793-802.
- LaFollette, Hugh, ed. *Ethics in practice: an anthology*. John Wiley & Sons, 2020.
- Ahmad, Abu Abdullah Ahmad bin Muhammad bin Hambal(241 A.H.), (Mu’ssasat ur Risalah 1421/2001), v.37, p. 341, Hadith No. 2668
- Aksoy, Sahin, and Abdurrahman Elmali. "The core concepts of the four principles of bioethics as found in Islamic tradition." *Med. & L.* 21 (2002): 211.
- Al- Tirmizi, Ch. Sifatil Qiyama, Hadith No. 2517, he added that this Hadith is Gharib(unusual).
- Al-Meesaq Al-Islami Al-’alami lil Akhlaqiyyat At Tibbiyyah, Ch. 5, Al-Qadhaya Alljtima’yyah, Taiseer ul Maut Ao Qatl il marhamah, Course.62
- Al-Qaradawi Y. Question and answer about Euthanasia. In: Islam online site. Available at: http://www.islamonline.net/servlet/Satellite?cid=1119503544774&pagename=IslamOnline-English-Ask_Scholar/FatwaE/FatwaEAskTheScholar. Accessed April 5, 2012.

¹⁰⁴ Surah Al-Mu’minun [23:14]

Al-Tirmizi, Muhammad bin Esa bin Saura(279 A.H.), Sunan Al-Tirmizi, (Darul Gharb Al- Islami, Beirut, 1998), vol. 4, p. 180, Hadith No. 2572.

Aramesh, Kiarash, and Heydar Shadi. "Euthanasia: an Islamic ethical perspective." (2007): 35-38.

Aramesh, Kiarash, and Heydar Shadi. "Euthanasia: an Islamic ethical perspective." (2007): 35-38.

Bachman, Jerald G., Kirsten H. Alcser, David J. Doukas, Richard L. Lichtenstein, Amy D. Corning, and Howard Brody. "Attitudes of Michigan physicians and the public toward legalizing physician-assisted suicide and voluntary euthanasia." *New England Journal of Medicine* 334, no. 5 (1996): 303-309.

Coward, Harold G., Julius Lipner, and Katherine K. Young. *Hindu ethics: Purity, abortion, and euthanasia*. SUNY Press, 1989.

Daar, Abdallah S., and A. Khitamy. "Bioethics for clinicians: 21. Islamic bioethics." *Cmaj* 164, no. 1 (2001): 60-63.

Ecclesiastes, 7:17

Emanuel, Ezekiel J., Diane L. Fairclough, and Linda L. Emanuel. "Attitudes and desires related to euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide among terminally ill patients and their caregivers." *Jama* 284, no. 19 (2000): 2460-2468.

Engelhardt, H. Tristram, and Ana Smith Iltis. "End-of-life: the traditional Christian view." *The Lancet* 366, no. 9490 (2005): 1045-1049.

Førde, Reidun, Olaf Gjerløw Aasland, and Erik Falkum. "The ethics of euthanasia—attitudes and practice among Norwegian physicians." *Social science & medicine* 45, no. 6 (1997): 887-892.

Fosarelli, Pat. "The Sanctity of Human Life." *JAMA* 298, no. 24 (2007): 2914-2920.

Goma Ali. Ethics of Euthanasia. Available at:<http://www.islamopediaonline.org/fatwa/egypts-darul-ifta-euthanasia>. Accessed April 5,2012.

Hathout, Hassan. "Islamic basis for biomedical ethics." (1992).
<http://hospicecare.com/about-iahpc/publications/ethical-issues-2/otherpublications/ the-double-effect-of-pain-medication-separating-myth-from-reality/>.
<http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/double-effect/>.
<http://www.sehha.com/medical/IslamicCodeEthics5b.htm>

Ibid

Ibid, and Al-Mosu'h Al-Fiqhiyyah Al-Kuwaitiyyah v.3, p. 154

Ibid, v.1, p. 25.

Ibid, v.1, p. 300

Ibn Majjah, Hadith No. 2340-2342.

Ibn Qadamah, Abu Muhammad Muwaffiq ud Din Al-Muqaddisi (620A.H.), AlMughni, (Maktabat ul Cairo), v.5, p. 390

Jami' Tirmizi, Vol. 2, p.371, Hadith No. 1068.

Kane, Leslie. "MA, Exclusive Ethics Survey Results: Doctors Struggle With Tougher-Than-Ever Dilemmas." *Medscape Medical Ethics* 2010 (2010)..

Lajnatul Ulema(Scholar's Commettee), Al-Mosu'h Al-Fiqhiyyah Al-Kuwaitiyyah (Wazarat ul Aqaf wa Al-Sho'on Al-Islamiyyah, Darus Salasil, Kuwait), v. 17, p. 101

Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

Langrial, Altaf Hussain, and Muhammad Muslim. "LEGITIMACY OF EUTHANASIA (MERCY KILLING): AN ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVES."

Majallah Al-Ahkam Al-Adaliyyah, vol.1, p.16.

Mayda, Atilla Senih, Erdem Özkara, and Funda Corapçioğlu. "Attitudes of oncologists toward euthanasia in Turkey." *Palliative & supportive care* 3, no. 3 (2005): 221-225.

Mubarak, Qais bin Muhammad A'l Al-Sheikh, Al-Tadavi wal Mas'ooliyyah AITaibbiyyah fi Al-Sharia'h Al-Islamiyyah(Mu'ssasat ur Rayyan, 1997), p. 99.

Narimisa, 2014

Narimisa, Mehran. "Euthanasia in Islamic views." *European Scientific Journal* (2014).

Narimisa, Mehran. "Euthanasia in Islamic views." *European Scientific Journal* (2014).

Narimisa, Mehran. "Euthanasia in Islamic views." *European Scientific Journal* (2014).

Nida, Muhammad Naeem, Maut ud Dmagh(Bait ut Tibb wal Islam, Dar ul fikr), p. 197.

Pereira, Jose. "Legalizing euthanasia or assisted suicide: the illusion of safeguards and controls." *Current Oncology* 18, no. 2 (2011): 38-45.

Pioneering NUS study unveils what Singapore doctors say about caring for the dying. Available at: www.lienfoundation.org/pdf/news/. Accessed on Feb 20, 2012.

Rachels, James. "Active and passive euthanasia." *Bioethics: An Introduction to the History, Methods, and Practice* (1975): 77-82.

Sachedina Islam. In: Reich WT, editor. *Encyclopedia of bioethics*. Rev ed. New York: Simon and Schuster/Prentice Hall International 1995:1289-97.

Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "End-of-life: the Islamic view." *The Lancet* 366, no. 9487 (2005): 774-779.

Sachedina, Abdulaziz. "Right to Die?": Muslim Views about End-of-Life Decisions." *Internet* Available from: <http://www.people.virginia.edu/~aas/article/article3/htm> (2006).

Sahih Bukhari, v1, p.

Sahih Bukhari, v2, p 96, Hadith No. 1363

Sahih Bukhari, vol.1, p.18, Hadith No.18.

Sahih Bukhari, Vol.2, p. 96, Hadith No. 1363

Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 114, Hadith No. 5640.

Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 114, Hadith No. 5641.

Sahih Bukhari, vol.7, p. 115, Hadith No. 5647.

Sahih Muslim, vol. 4, p. 1993, Hadith No. 2575

Sahih Muslim, vol. 4, p.1993, Hadith No. 2574.

Sahih Muslim, vol. 4,, p 1991, Hadith No. 2572

Seale, Clive. "Legalisation of euthanasia or physician-assisted suicide: survey of doctors' attitudes." *Palliative Medicine* 23, no. 3 (2009): 205-212.

Suarez-Almazor, Maria E., Michelle Belzile, and Eduardo Bruera. "Euthanasia and physician-assisted suicide: a comparative survey of physicians, terminally ill cancer patients, and the general population." *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 15, no. 2 (1997): 418-427.

Sunan Abi Dau'd, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No.3357, Jami' Al-Tirmizi, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No. 1961, Sunan Ibn e Majah, Kitab al-Tibb, Hadith No. 3427.

Sunan Abi Dawuud. Vol. 2, Book 27, Kitab al-Tibb, Chapter 1, Hadith 3855. Available at: <http://www.muhammad.org>. Accessed February 20, 2012.

Sunan Ibn e Majah, v.1. P. 516, Hadith No. 1616

Sunan Ibn e Majah, V3, p 582, Hadith No. 254.

Surah Al- Baqara, 2 : 11-12.

Surah Al-Asra, 103 : 31

Surah Al-Baqara, 2:195.

Surah Al-Mu'minun, 23:14.

The sanctity of human life. In: Islamic code of ethics. In Islamset site. Available at: <http://www.islamset.com/ethics/code/cont2.html>. Accessed April 4, 2012.

Ulema Committee formed by Usmani Caliphate, Majallat ul Ahkam Al- Adaliyyah, (Noor Muhammad Karkhana Tijarat e Kutub, A'ram Bagh, Karachi), v.1, p.16

Van der Maas, Paul J., Gerrit Van Der Wal, Ilinka Haverkate, Carmen LM De Graaff, John GC Kester, Bregje D. Onwuteaka-Philipsen, Agnes Van Der Heide, Jacqueline M. Bosma, and Dick L. Willems. "Euthanasia, physician-assisted suicide, and other medical practices involving the end of life in the Netherlands, 1990–1995." *New England Journal of Medicine* 335, no. 22 (1996): 1699-1705.

Verkerk, Marian, Eric van Wijlick, Johan Legemaate, and Alexander de Graeff. "A national guideline for palliative sedation in the Netherlands." *Journal of pain and symptom management* 34, no. 6 (2007): 666-670.